

**IMPACT OF RACIAL DISCRIMINATION ON THE COLORED AND BLACK SOUTH
AFRICANS DURING APARTHEID TIME IN THE NOVELS OF NADINE GORDIMER'S**

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ABSTRACT

Nadine Gordimer narrates the history of apartheid in South Africa in her novels. Her critical realism that emanates from her close and critical observation of people and their lives sets her in the position of anti-apartheid novelist. Her novels are the metaphoric representation of people who either are in distress for being separated from the majority of the society-like whites- or suffer from imposed deprivation like the blacks. As a novelist, she operates like a “sensitive needle”, giving a voice to the conscience of her context. She is the writer of commitment and in her novels, she testifies to the predicaments of her society marked by political issues during apartheid. Gordimer’s literary output serves as a metaphoric means through which she expresses her protest against oppression and votes for equality and liberation. She is also an observant witness whose writings reflect the depths of her people’s consciousness and lay bare their psycho-political development. In her authentic portraits of South Africa, Gordimer calls for a radical change, a transformation inevitable for the betterment of her fragmented society.

The rise of agony and hatred among people in South Africa were the results of the racist laws practiced during apartheid regime. The apartheid was very typical to South Africa. The demonstrations and revolts of the blacks aroused as reaction to such laws. The ideology of racial laws aimed to divide the society into many racial groups according to the color bar. The government maintains the ideology to be practiced in the real life situation by separating the whites from the blacks. Thus, race and identity became the main components in Gordimer’s novels.

Her novels are metaphoric testimonies of the South African context in which she targets all ends and means of discrimination and denigration. These qualities are reflected also in *My Son’s Story* through the depiction of the colored family of Sonny. The couple, Aila and Sonny’s life is built on solidarity. Gordimer emphasizes this to make couple’s fate more ironic and their break-up poignant. Ironically, what unites a couple might divide it. The couple’s union is based on love, mutual desire and on well-established family structure. In *My Son’s Story*, Gordimer tries to analyze the situation of peoples in South Africa to describe not only the radicalization and growth of particular people, but also the way that the most friendly relations influenced by racial discrimination and colored problems among classes divided the people under the apartheid government. Thus, Gordimer produces a sensitive novel, which deals with the multi-racial society in South Africa.

Key Words: Nadine Gordimer, South African society, black and white colour, prominent

INTRODUCTION

This study presents largely the core of apartheid policy and its practices on South African society. This

work brings out a brief historical sketch of South Africa and focuses mainly on the impacts of apartheid and racial segregation that affected the lives of South African people. Racial discrimination and political exclusion for the blacks were the components of apartheid ideology that enabled the white states to impose racial laws in South Africa. These white states aggressively controlled the lives of South African people. The black South Africans were treated by the whites as brutes and were reduced to the conditions of animals. This gave rise to confusion, violence and conflict between the whites and the blacks in South Africa.

From the literary point of view, it highlights some prominent writers who lived and witnessed segregation and apartheid era. These writers, either black or white, had an anti-apartheid stand. Moreover, it takes into account in brief the historical literary facts, which represent the suffering of South African black people during the segregationist laws of the white government.

Nadine Gordimer comes out as the most creative writer to write fiction from the long experience of apartheid. Her worldwide literary eminence is achieved by her role within South Africa as an activist in the culture of resistance, and an articulate antagonist of censorship, detention without trial, and Bantu education, and as a tireless organizer of writers across the racial partitions. Gordimer's importance is the equivalence between the beginnings of her career as writer and the rise to power of the dominated *National Party*, which has ruled South Africa continuously since 1948. Her thirteen novels, hundreds of short stories, and copious essays of political and literary comments offer a uniquely creative record of the era of apartheid in South Africa. This record gains depth from Gordimer's acute sensitivity to the history of her times. Among many South African contemporary writers in English, she shows an unequalled ability to combine the shifting political tempers of her society into the very form and texture of her fiction.

Nadine Gordimer's portrayals of the structure and experience of apartheid are well known, and have received much critical attention. Nadine Gordimer received Nobel Prize for Literature in 1991. Most of Nadine Gordimer's works deal with the moral and psychological tensions of her racially divided home country. She was a founding member of *Congress of South African Writers*, and even at the height of the apartheid regime, she never considered going into exile.

Nadine Gordimer was born of Jewish parents on 20 November 1923 in Springs, a gold-mining town outside Johannesburg, South Africa. Her father had fled the czarist anti-Semitism of Lithuania and in Springs he learned watch making and became a jeweler. Her mother was born in England. Thus, Springs town was the setting for Gordimer's first novel, *The Lying Days* (1953). From her early childhood, Gordimer witnessed how the white minority increasingly weakened the rights of the black majority.

Gordimer shows in her novels a wide series of diverse voices telling how people experienced racial history in South Africa, different perspectives that give a profound understanding of the second half of the twentieth century up to the elimination of apartheid, and show the junction of private lives and the municipal history of South Africa. Her novels thus pretend in acute form the question of whose story will be told, and who will tell it. Bruce King, in an analysis of the evolution of Gordimer's novels, asserts, "*the novel form evolved to become increasingly 'postmodern' and multivoiced*" (3). This diversity of voices and the corresponding shifts in viewpoint, obvious in each of the novels, provide ways to explore the close connection between the personal and the political. Aware of the possibilities of viewpoint manipulation, the writer often exhibits alternating points of view that show from very different

perspectives how people were influenced and determined by the politics of South Africa. The flexibility in her manipulation of point of view in portraying the effects of apartheid and political history of South African people is observed in most of her works especially novels that are taken for the study.

Gordimer was a patriot and proud to be an African. Gordimer has repeatedly stated her view of what it means to be African in terms of an inclusive, indigenous culture. She clearly did not see herself as a European, despite her European roots. However, as a white who identifies herself as an African and is committed to a common culture with blacks.

Being a writer in South Africa, Gordimer has been complicated by the censorship laws, which were designed to stop the publication, not only on authors' works but also on publishers as well. Gordimer has spoken out many times against censors. She is quite correct to point out the political reason for censorship and banning of book by South African writers:

. . . All those books by South African writers which have been banned, have been banned for a political reason: non-conformity with the picture of South African life as prescribed and proscribed by apartheid (Gordimer, Telling Times 122).

Gordimer defines protest as:

... arising as an ancillary to political opposition in situations where the political machinery is defective in allowing opposition its due voice and corrective influence (Gordimer, and Clingman 89).

In other words, Gordimer argues that the South African culture of protest arose accurately because of the apartheid government's enforced repression of ideas. In a country where citizens may not express political opinions, they are forced to give voice to their opinions in alternative forms. Such powerful alternative form is literature.

Nadine Gordimer was very optimistic that Black South Africans would free themselves and live free in due course of time. She prophesied in her short story *Some Monday for Sure*:

I knew it must be a Monday. I notice that women quite often don't remember ordinary things like this, I don't know what they think about- for instance, Emmadidn't catch on that it must be Monday, next Monday or the one after, some Monday for sure, because Monday was the day that we knew Josias went with the truck to the Free State mines (125).

She suggested that on some day, for sure, black South Africans would free themselves and rule themselves. History has borne out her belief, yet the observation that the day was ordinary is true after the guerilla activity of more than a decade. This day came true in May 1994.

Gordimer's apartheid writings had an easier relation to social and historical realities and clearer connections, which she deemed necessary for the fidelity with which the writer depicts his/her times. Her novels, short stories, and even essays of the apartheid years were clearly political in their opposition to apartheid. She saw writing as a liberating political act that legitimates itself through the authority of history. Nadine Gordimer made a distinction for herself as an author by undertaking an outstanding position in literature as a privileged, white female writer supporting the dilemma of poor black South

Nadine Gordimer's apartheid writings were of active treatment of apartheid themes. Really, Gordimer easily aligned herself with the fate of her country and its turbulent history and has dedicated her apartheid writings to document its history.

This study deals with racial discrimination and colored identity in Gordimer's *My Son's Story* (1990). It examines the impact of racial discrimination on the colored and black South Africans during apartheid time.

RACIAL DISCRIMINATION AND COLORED IDENTITY

Racial discrimination in South Africa is unique in the world. The black communities in South Africa were against racism and the policy of their government. Identity is the other problem for the black and colored South Africans during apartheid regime. Apartheid is generally understood as comprising a set of racially discriminatory policies and enforced racial segregation. It covered all the aspects of life in South Africa, political, social, and economical. As South Africa has a long history of foreign occupation, settlement and urbanization, this led to a literature of protest, inequality and discrimination under apartheid. South African literature became one of the main areas as a battle against apartheid.

My Son's Story is about the black people in South Africa who fought for the freedom of the blacks. This novel successfully depicts what a horrible life was lived under racial discrimination and apartheid.

My Son's Story attempts to study the situation in South Africa to describe not only the radicalization and growth of particular people, but also the way that the most intimate relations affected by racial discrimination among classes divided the people under the apartheid Government. Of course, racial sentiment among blacks and whites is crucial reality. The novel is about the reality of what makes life easy for some people and hard for others.

It is about the ways in which political commitment slowly but ineluctably transformed the lives of four members of a black South African family: Will, the son, tells the story of his father and is the narrator of the story. Sonny, the father, transforms himself from a schoolteacher to a revolutionary leader and the orator for the struggle against apartheid. Baby, the daughter, and Aila, the mother, become great activists against apartheid in the later part of their lives. This colored family is against apartheid.

Sonny is a schoolteacher of colored students. Sonny, who is a great lover of arts and Shakespeare, is not allowed to enter the public library. Whereas, the whites are allowed to use it. While being aware about the suffering of his community racially and politically, he decides to participate with his students in protesting against segregation and oppression of the whites against the blacks. In this way, Sonny becomes a fulltime activist, and a hero in the struggle for freedom and liberation from apartheid and racial discrimination.

The couple (Sonny and Aila) was like the other blacks. They go every Saturday to buy from the white people. In addition, in the city of white people, the couple with their children goes around the city. Their intention of watching a movie is frustrated as they are forbidden to enter the theatre. The blacks were accustomed to closeness. In queues for transport, for work permits, for housing allocation, for all the

stamped paper that authorized their lives: *loaded into overcrowded trains and buses to take them back and forth across the veld, fitting a family into one room, they cannot keep the outline of space – another, invisible skin* – (Gordimer, *My Son's Story* 110) shows that for South African whites, conditions are fundamentally different, but that they pay a price for their privilege. Gordimer depicts the African women in all their misery and ugliness:

How black they always were, these women; black blackened by labour in the sun, it's as if nature, which supplied our founding parents with the right degree of pigment to inhabit this continent, also supplies them with the camouflage under which to appear to submit to slavery ... she strips the green leaves and spills the floss. If you're mixed you don't have the protection back from the cobs, digging her earth-rimmed nail to spurt milk from a row of nubs, because I ask her for young mealies, and her black face has no recognition for me... (144).

According to Gordimer, color is central to every human transaction. She ironically narrates the color and the woman in transaction. To buy a mealie from a street vender is to note her colour. To note her color is to consider the implications of color and to measure one's own relation to these implications.

Gordimer elaborates racial discrimination in her novel *My Son's Story*. She represents the situation of Sonny:

The lover of Shakespeare never had the right to enter the municipal library and so did not so much as think about it while white people came out before him with books under their arms (12).

This statement is an evidence that Sonny as a colored teacher and a great lover of Shakespeare could not enter the library to enjoy Shakespeare's works. These lines strongly represent the sensitive kind of racial discrimination against colored people in South Africa. Sonny thinks very keenly of the library building and what significance it has for him. If he is not allowed to enter, what is the use of his standing in front of the library's door? The situation of his standing is creating a kind of pathos and sympathy. Sonny is looking at the whites coming out from the library carrying books in their hands. It can be said that the whites have the right to enter the library very easily, whereas, the blacks have no right to do so. Because of this, the colored family increased its efforts to fight for the rights in the racist society.

The picture of racial discrimination in the novel can be seen in many passages. The novel, *My Son's Story*, describes the colored schoolteacher Sonny and his family situated as marginalized from white society:

As some lordly wild animal marks the boundaries of his hunting and mating ground which no other may cross, it was as if the municipality left some warning odour, scent of immutable authority, where the Saturday people were not to transgress. And they read the scent (12).

Gordimer shows in this passage the strict racial separations between whites and non-whites in South Africa.

Because of the strict laws of racial discrimination in South Africa, Sonny deceives, betrays and deserts the public for the private. Sonny first betrays his community through his physically moving away from his community. Then, he betrays his family for his mistress, Hannah. Sonny leaves his wife and

children, Will and Baby, because of such strict racial laws enacted in South Africa. In this way, racial discrimination forces the family to live apart from one another leading to their aimless life. For this, Will blames the laws of racial discrimination.

Apartheid pervaded South African culture as well as laws. The apartheid policy prohibited the blacks from getting jobs. They were not allowed to run business or professional practices in areas designated for the whites. The blacks were not allowed to enter cinemas, restaurants and hotels in the white areas. Blacks are obliged to live in separate townships, slums and ghettos outside the white areas. Sonny and his family members are living in the same ghettos where blacks live. Blacks live in wretched conditions. They do not enjoy their lives in the townships, as they are always slaves to the whites. Gordimer depicts the wretched situation of the blacks living in ghettos. The narrative voice of Will highlights his father's help for people of his kind:

Where people lived in wretched conditions in a ghetto he was one who would be sent to help them set up a residents' association; when they understood that a rent boycott was a good way to protest, he would be among those to teach them how to organize the campaign (66).

The pertinent question that arises out of the foregoing discussion is the color identity and how is it relevant to the thematic discussion of Nadine Gordimer's *My Son's Story*?

The color identity in *My Son's Story* is open to many different shades of meaning. It might be taken to mean 'mixed race', 'half-breed', 'half-caste' or mulatto. Mulatto is the one who inherits color between white and black ancestors. According to Gavin Lewis colored is an administrative invention. It is to divide blacks and preserve white "racial purity" by treating coloreds as a separate and uniformed "race" separate from both Africans and whites (Lewis 3). In spite of this distinction, it is bewildering to distinguish who or what 'colored' people are. Over the years the white and the black have mixed up so intractably that, the 'colored' community distinct from the European does not exist 'in any realistic term' as Marais has argued (Marais 283). Though the white community has struggled to keep its distinct identity, it has mixed up as the waters do at the confluence of two rivers. The attempt at the segregation between the white and the black people was done during the apartheid era.

My Son's Story deals with 'colored identity' around a 'colored' family, and a colored narrator. The focus on the 'colored' family is important only because the mixture of the variable and the changeable of the term 'colored' facilitate the kinds of substitutions in the identity and perception that the narrator envisages. Its instability and flexibility as a racial distinction suggests that the novelist is experimenting with the possibility of transformation in the racial order that permeates all personal, gender and sexual relations in South Africa.

CONCLUSION

The South African white racial superiority is complicated vis a vis the South African black race. On the one hand, the black African race was on the edge of racial brink. For example, the great obstacles prohibiting 'colored' advancement into white society of 'colored' voters, and the compulsory residential segregation in the towns of Cape Province were great hurdles in the way of the blacks. The political power was bestowed on the 'colored' in the Cape Province because of their majority and consequently they got not only the political power but also security of life. 'Colored' political organization such as the *African*

Political Organization (APO) had a great impact on the political mobilization of opposition grounds, although they appealed for support and their activities were restricted to 'colored' people.

The 'colored' identity was imposed identity. Some of the elite, political, and cultural organizations of the 'colored' communities adopted it as a means to advance their own interest as a group. There were 'colored' organizations, which demanded integration into white society.

In *My Son's Story*, Gordimer has examined whether the whites have many privileges than the blacks or a few privileges than the blacks. Still then it cannot be any equality with the whites. This has given rise to intense tension, which has resulted, into life and death problem to the 'colored':

Not defined – and it was this lack of definition in itself that was never to be questioned, but observed like a taboo, something which no one, while following, ever could admit to (Gordimer, *My Son's Story* 21-22).

Will's narrative arises out of deep consciousness of his feelings for 'colored' people. He appears to be self-divided between the black and the white blood. It indicates his bewildering situation about the 'colored' people in the country, therefore, his imprecation over the black 'color' shows his tension surrounding his 'colored' identity.

Gordimer sees the 'colored' family has a small margin between white community and Black location. In *My Son's Story*, Gordimer's thematic preoccupation is with the politics of race, gender and sexuality. She raises the question of hybridity and fluidity against the historical conditions of 'colored' people.

The 'colored' family in *My Son's Story* makes the symbolic move of crossing the border from the 'colored' location in their hometown to a 'grey area' (Gordimer *My Son's Story* 14): "*She entered our house when he was in detention. ... when we moved to the city my father had bought that house in what later was called a 'grey area' where people of our kind defied the law and settled in among whites*" (14). The 'colored' family was allowed to move into the grey area of the white city. It shows that the 'colored' identity is hybrid, fluid and faulty. Johannesburg is a city where the white working class moves out for better life. The committee gives a house for Sonny's family to stay near the white community. This makes the whites think that it is a challenge to the white people. It is because the white come to stay in the grey area to upgrade their standard of life. Consequently, it is a defiance of the whites by Sonny's family.

Gordimer's art of cultural negotiation projects a possibility of change, an alternative future for South Africa. Her imaginative writing also moves from simple binary metaphors of male and female. Her use of 'colored' characters is her attempt to develop the trans-ethnic values in her symbolic representation of the colored subject.

To sum up, Gordimer's narrative technique in *My Son's Story* is geared to achieve the truth of racial discrimination that black people suffer from in their homeland South Africa, and, the tragic consequences of apartheid in affecting the most intimate of personal relationships. Moreover, it traces the imposed domination on black mind and body. This domination may be of the openly aggressive sort, such as the jailing of black activists and the imprisonment of black people in ghettos. The novel *My Son's Story* depicts the active involvement of colored community in the freedom movement.

My Son's Story discusses the miserable situation of Sonny's colored family. In the family, the head, Sonny was pushed into a revolutionary role first by his students' rebellion and later by his beloved Hannah's activity of anti-apartheid movement. Aila, the real wife of Sonny pushed herself to a revolutionary role also. She reflects the ideal example as a wife, household, and activist against apartheid.

Will, the son, is the narrator of his father's story. He is the mediator who tries to close the faults of his father towards the family when Sonny fell in love with Hannah. Through this colored family, Gordimer draws the different types of racism that had been practiced on the coloreds in the land of South Africa at the time of apartheid. Through the novel, it is realized largely that the whites are superior to the blacks. The whites think that they are the best creators in the world whereas the blacks must be the servants to the whites. The whites in South African society forget that all people are equal in the eyes of God. That is the climax of degradation for human beings.

My Son's Story is regarded as a milestone in Gordimer's literary career for which she got the Nobel Prize. Furthermore, it depicts the active involvement of colored community in the freedom movement. Actually, South African identity was the notion of African novelists. Gordimer's highly symbolic language and fragmented structures reflected the cultural experience of being black woman or man in Africa showing a specific cultural, economic, and political response to the situation.

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